

from alcohol-water gave reasonable yield (60-65%) of the compounds of the type II and III.

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Electrometric Studies of Rare Earth Complexes of *N*-Salicylideneorphanilic Acid

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No work on the reactions of rare earth metals with *N*-salicylideneorphanilic acid (H_2SO) is reported in the existing literature. The present investigations are aimed at to determine the composition and stability constants of the La (III), Ce (III), Pr(III), Nd (III), Sm (III) and Gd (III) complexes

and stability constants of the complexes. For this purpose following solutions were titrated separately against 0.1M NaOH keeping total volume as 40.0 ml (1) 10.0 ml 0.01M H_2SO +4.0 ml 1.0M $NaClO_4$ +26.0 ml water, (2) 10.0 ml 0.01M H_2SO +4.0 ml 1.0M $NaClO_4$ +10.0 ml 0.01M $M(NO_3)_3$ +16.0 ml water, (3) 10.0 ml 0.01M H_2SO +4.0 ml 1.0M $NaClO_4$ +5.0 ml 0.01M $M(NO_3)_3$ +21.0 ml water.

The mean values of dissociation constants (pK_1 & pK_2) as obtained by Algebraic method⁴ and Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values method have been found to be 2.05 and 8.13. The formation curves of the rare earth metal complexes representing $\bar{n}$ as a function of $-\log[A^{-2}]$ suggest the formation of 1:2 complex. Refinement of the approximate values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was done by computational methods⁵ and the values obtained by all the methods are in fair agreement as shown in Table 1 in which the values of overall free energy changes at 25° are also included.

The stability of the complexes of the metals, having similar electronic configurations, increases with decreasing ionic size. This trend is also observed in the present case (Table 1) as the sequence of stability found is, La < Ce < Pr < Nd < Sm < Gd.

The rare earth complexes studied above have been isolated in the solid state by the method reported earlier.⁶ These compounds were analysed and their molecular weights and magnetic moments were determined. The results thus obtained are summarized in Table 2.

Table 1. Stability constants of trivalent metal complexes as H_2SO

Temperature = 25° ± 0.1°		$\mu = 0.1M NaClO_4$						
Metals		A	B	C	D	E	F	$-\Delta F$ K. Cal/mole
La(III)	log K_1	3.75	3.71	3.68	3.75	3.75	3.73	8.86
	log K_2	2.75	2.72	2.68	2.75	2.75	2.73	
Ce(III)	log K_1	4.26	4.22	4.20	4.26	4.26	4.24	10.77
	log K_2	3.63	3.60	3.57	3.63	3.63	3.61	
Pr(III)	log K_1	4.45	4.42	4.39	4.45	4.45	4.43	11.40
	log K_2	3.90	3.87	3.85	3.90	3.90	3.88	
Nd(III)	log K_1	5.12	5.10	5.07	5.11	5.12	5.10	12.96
	log K_2	4.36	4.32	4.30	4.37	4.36	4.34	
Sm(III)	log K_1	5.55	5.53	5.50	5.55	5.55	5.54	13.79
	log K_2	4.54	4.50	4.48	4.53	4.53	4.51	
Gd(III)	log K_1	5.81	5.78	5.75	5.81	5.80	5.79	14.33
	log K_2	4.66	4.63	4.61	4.66	4.68	4.65	

where A = Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values; B = Interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values; C = Correction term; D = Successive approximation; E = Convergence formula; F = Average value; and $-\Delta F$ = Overall changes in free energy.

with *N*-salicylideneorphanilic acid (H_2SO). H_2SO was prepared by a general procedure as reported earlier¹.

Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique^{2,3} was followed to study the dissociation constants of H_2SO

The La(III) complex is found diamagnetic, as expected.

Considering elemental analyses, potentiometric, conductometric, and magnetic data it was found that

TABLE 2. ANALYSES AND μ_{eff} VALUES OF THE H₂SO COMPLEXES OF La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III) AND Gd(III)

Complexes	Analyses				μ_{eff} B.M. at 298°K
	Found %		Required %		
	N	Metal	N	Metal	
[LaC ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₈]	3.98	20.07	4.05	20.13	—
[CeC ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₈]	3.98	20.26	4.04	20.34	2.22
[PrC ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₈]	3.97	20.28	4.04	20.36	3.35
[NdC ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₈]	3.95	20.62	4.02	20.76	3.58
[SmC ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₈]	3.89	21.34	3.97	21.43	1.58
[GdC ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₈]	3.85	22.03	3.95	22.17	7.80

all these complexes possess 1:2 metal-ligand stoichiometry.

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Analytical Applications of Schiff Base Copper Complexes. Gravimetric Estimation of Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba*

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MIXED metal complexes of Schiff bases of 3 formyl salicylic acid (3FSA) and ethylene diamine (en) 1, 2 diaminopropane (DAP) or 1, 2 diamino 2-methyl propane (DAMP) have been thoroughly investigated by Rawat and Phillips¹.

The complexes containing a co-ordinated copper ion associated with a second metal ion which could be an alkali metal, alkaline earth metal or a transition metal ion. A few metal complexes of Schiff bases 3FSA with en were first reported by Poddar². During the course of investigation it was observed that elements like Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba can be quantitatively precipitated by the [enLCu]Na₂, [DAPL Cu]Na₂ or [DAMPL Cu]Na₂ Complex as [enLCuX], [DAPL

Cu X], and [DAMPL Cu X] where X = Mg, Ca, Sr or Ba. In the present communication the analytical use of Schiff base metal complexes for the gravimetric determination of Mg, Ca, Sr, and Ba has been described.

[en L Cu]Na₂, R = R' = H for en
 [DAPL Cu]Na₂, R = H, R' = CH₃ for DAP
 [DAMPL Cu]Na₂, R = R' = CH₃ for DAMP

Colour of the complex is violet to blue, decomposes above 250° and magnetic moment is about 2.0 B.M. at 298°K.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. quality. 3FSA was prepared from salicylic acid and hexamine by the method of Duff and Bills³ and this was allowed to react in alcoholic solution with twice the gram mol of en, DAP or DAMP to prepare the Schiff base as suggested by Poddar⁴. The water soluble complexes of [en L Cu]Na₂, [DAPL Cu]Na₂ and [DAMPL Cu]Na₂ are the basic compounds which were used as analytical reagents. The Na₂ Cu complex of the Schiff base was obtained by mixing alcoholic solution of A.R. copper acetate to the caustic soda solution of the Schiff base. The beautiful violet colour complex obtained was quite stable in the air. It was washed with small quantity of alcohol on the goocherucible and dried in vacuo for sometime and later heated to 120° in an oven. The complexes are hydrated to different degrees but heating them first in vacuo for about 2 hr and then for about 2 hr in an oven at 120° gave water free complexes. The dry complexes were used for the quantitative estimation of Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba at about a pH of 5 to 7. The highly acidic solution leads to the formation of H₂Cu complexes.

Estimation of Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba. Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba salts contain .001M and aqueous solutions were prepared. 50 ml of this solution was taken and diluted to

*The work was carried out partly at the School of Chemistry, University of New South Wales, Australia.